

Deliverable 17.1

Training material for the use of AAAI for TREs pilot implementation

Project Title (Grant agreement number)	EOSC-ENTRUST Grant Agreement 101131056		
Project Acronym (EC call)	EOSC-ENTRUST		
WP No & Title	WP17: Technologies		
WP Leaders	Luděk Matyska (MUNI)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	MUNI		
Contractual delivery date	31/08/2025	Actual delivery date	31/10/2025
Delayed	Yes		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	CSC, GRNET		
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1. Executive Summary

The EOSC-ENTRUST AAI for Trusted Research Environments (TREs) training materials provide basic introductory information for users on how to properly use the Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAI) in its piloting phase. The ENTRUST AAI is derived from the Life Science AAI (LS AAI), also known as LS Login [6], which is the federated authentication and authorisation infrastructure that enables life-science researchers to sign in using their home organisation credentials or community or commercial identities (e.g. ORCID). This deliverable focuses on new features, as described in the EOSC-ENTRUST AAI for TREs Blueprint [1], and provides an overall background necessary for a better understanding of ENTRUST AAI, thus improving its use.

The deliverable should be considered a first version of the training materials, as in some cases – e.g., the Accounting service – it precedes the actual implementation. The purpose is to allow users to start using the ENTRUST AAI during the pilots and demonstration that will provide the necessary feedback both for the evolution of the ENTRUST AAI Blueprint and also the actual implementation, whose features will be gradually propagated into the future versions of this deliverable.

The deliverable itself comprises four parts: this document, which serves as an introduction, explanation, and general background source, and three appendices that provide specific information for the three different user roles we identified for this purpose: the TRE administrator, the ENTRUST AAI user, and the VO manager, respectively. The latter refers to individuals responsible for managing group or project memberships, access policies, and enrollment workflows within the virtual organisations integrated with the ENTRUST AAI (e.g. those established for specific Trusted Research Environments or scientific collaborations). As the ENTRUST AAI implementation is a clone of the LS AAI [6], this deliverable deliberately references relevant materials for the use of LS AAI (again, see [6]) and focuses on the relevant TRE-related information. This allows us to keep this deliverable compact as a first version that will evolve together with the TRE AAI implementation and its piloting through the EOSC-ENTRUST project. Additionally, referencing materials instead of copying them from LS AAI ensures that these training materials are automatically updated to reflect the evolution of LS AAI.

The primary role of this deliverable is to provide (together with appendices and training materials already available for the LS AAI) an entry point for those who are participating in the EOSC-ENTRUST pilots, are expected to work with the ENTRUST AAI in any of its roles, and need a concise introduction to the proper use of the ENTRUST AAI implementation during a period of rapid evolution. The wider community can use them as an introduction to the ENTRUST AAI for TREs, together with the blueprint, to better understand the

potential; however, this version of the deliverable should not be interpreted as standalone training material for a mature service in production use.

Users are expected to begin with this overview document, continue with the appendix corresponding to their role, and consult the relevant Life Science AAI documentation for detailed, step-by-step configuration and operational procedures.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'.]

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	Yes
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	Yes
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No

<p>Objective 2</p> <p>Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.</p>	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	No
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	No
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

Objective 4 The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	No
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	No

3. Methods

The training material has been developed as a set of four interconnected documents addressing different user roles within the EOSC ENTRUST **Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI)** framework. The objective was to provide practical, role-oriented guidance while avoiding duplication of detailed technical documentation already available in other parts of the project, particularly within the **Life Science AAI (LS AAI)** ecosystem [6].

The structure and terminology of the training material are directly aligned with the **AAAI for TREs Blueprint** [1], which defines the architectural model and key components of the infrastructure. Existing **LS AAI** documentation [5, 6, 7] served as a baseline for those parts of AAAI that are functionally inherited, ensuring compatibility and consistency with current production services. New content was created only where ENTRUST introduces extensions or pilot functionalities, notably the **Accounting for Auditing** concept.

Therefore, instead of repeating the information and material already available for the LS AAI [5], we opted for a brief description of the necessary points, focusing on the relevant TRE-related information, and delegating users to the LS AAI information for a broader context. This allows us to keep this deliverable compact and make it just a first version that will evolve together with the ENTRUST AAAI implementation and its piloting through the

EOSC-ENTRUST project. Also, referencing instead of copying materials from LS AAI keeps these training materials automatically up to date with respect to the evolution of the LS AAI itself.

Scope and audience

We identified three different roles a person can have when operating or using the ENTRUST AAI:

- **TRE administrator**, a person responsible for managing and operating a TRE, and interested in connecting their TRE to the TRE AAI infrastructure. For this user, we expect appropriate technical knowledge and experience, while we focus primarily on the underlying principles, the knowledge requirements that a TRE administrator should know or consider before starting the process of connecting a TRE to the AAI.
- **ENTRUST AAI user**, a person who authenticates through the ENTRUST AAI for his/her identification and who may provide additional information (attributes) necessary for the access control decision.
- **VO manager**, a person who sets up and manages a Virtual Organization² within the AAI system, i.e., who defines and maintains VO membership and entitlement information (attributes) [9].

Structure

The main D17.1 document introduces the overall concept, describes the context of AAI training within EOSC ENTRUST, and refers readers to the appropriate appendices according to their role. The three appendices (A–C) provide targeted instructions and examples adapted to the expected technical background of each user group.

Sources and alignment

The EOSC-ENTRUST AAI derives directly from the LS AAI and follows the architectural principles defined in the **AAI for TREs Blueprint**. The implementation builds upon the LS AAI baseline while incorporating new features, most notably the **Accounting for Auditing** component. As this deliverable – the training materials – precedes the full implementation of the ENTRUST AAI, some components are intentionally omitted and will be described in later revisions once they are implemented and available. Particularly, the Accounting for Auditing service, which is currently in initial implementation stages, and these training

² Virtual Organisation (VO) refers to individuals responsible for managing group or project memberships, access policies, and enrollment workflows within the virtual organisations integrated with the ENTRUST AAI (e.g. those established for specific Trusted Research Environments or scientific collaborations).

materials could provide only elementary/introductory information about the ongoing implementation.

Policy and compliance baselines

To maintain interoperability and security alignment with existing research infrastructures, the training materials were prepared with reference to widely accepted policy and security frameworks:

- the **AARC-G069** Guidelines for expressing group membership and role information [9];
- the **WISE Baseline Acceptable Use Policy (AUP)** [10]; and
- the **Sirtfi v2** Security Incident Response Trust Framework [11].

These references ensure that the materials follow community best practices for federated identity management, authorisation, and incident response. TRE administrators and VO managers are expected to use them as supporting resources when aligning local procedures with the federated AAI environment.

Interaction with other work packages

The deliverable was prepared without specific interactions with the other work packages within the EOSC-ENTRUST project, as it primarily reflects the internal knowledge of the WP16/WP17. Broader WP interactions will follow during the actual deployment phase.

4. Work accomplished, including results

The work consisted of preparing and structuring the first version of **training material for the use of the AAI within Trusted Research Environments (TREs)**. The material aims to support pilot deployments conducted within the EOSC ENTRUST project and to provide a foundation for future iterations once the AAI reaches full production maturity.

The deliverable was created as a coherent set of four documents, each addressing a distinct audience and specific operational role, as described above in the Methods section:

- **Main document (D17.1):** provides overall context, defines scope, and introduces the role-specific appendices;
- **Appendix A:** *Training material for TRE administrators* [3] provides the necessary background needed for a TRE administrator to properly go through the process of integrating a TRE with the ENTRUST AAI system. It describes how authentication and authorisation are handled between the TRE and the AAI, as well as how to send accounting data to the Accounting Service. This appendix expects rather higher technology experience and know-how;

- **Appendix B:** *Training material for TRE users* [4] describes the different functionalities offered to the end-user by the AAAI. It covers account creation and registration, requesting access, and finally logging in to a TRE. It guides end-users through authentication and authorisation workflows;
- **Appendix C:** *Training material for VO managers* [5] explains VO and group management, entitlement definition, and coordination with TRE administrators. It is based on the Virtual Organization concept, where VO is a structure created within the AAAI that allows the aggregation and management of users, services, and resources for a specific purpose. The VO facilitates easy coordination of resources, management of user accounts, and setting access permissions, supporting effective collaboration on research initiatives. The document covers the VO lifecycle and the necessary duties of a VO manager, such as user membership management and auditing options available.

This first version of the training material focuses primarily on **conceptual understanding and procedural orientation**. The detailed operational instructions are already part of the LS AAAI documentation [6, 7, 8], so they are not repeated here.

Related work

Preparing the deliverable also triggered complementary work on a design document describing the details of the Accounting System within the AAAI ([2], work in progress, not a formal part of this deliverable). The goal of the latter document is to describe the design and implementation details for the accounting service within the ENTRUST TRE AAAI; these details are deliberately omitted from the EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI for TREs Blueprint [1] as the blueprint aims to be fully implementation agnostic.

5. Conclusions

This deliverable provides basic training materials for the use of the ENTRUST AAAI under development in the EOSC ENTRUST project. At this moment, the training materials target a rather specific group of people building and executing pilots and demonstrators within the project, providing them with sufficient information to connect the ENTRUST AAAI to the TREs, to use ENTRUST AAAI as the entry point, and also to manage the VOs and attributes (entitlements) needed for proper access control decisions.

The deliverable relies on the training materials (manuals, see [6, 7, 8]) available for the LS AAAI, as the ENTRUST AAAI implementation is derived from LS AAAI, and most of the use patterns are not different in ENTRUST AAAI.

6. Next steps

This deliverable is the first version, provided primarily for the people participating in the EOSC-ENTRUST demonstrators and prototypes, giving them sufficient information for proper integration and use within these pilots and demonstrations.

While the deliverable was prepared within WP17, we expect close interaction with WP20 and WP8 (and eventually WP11) to get feedback on the actual needs for the modification and expansion of the training materials.

The deliverable will be gradually evolved following the actual version of the ENTRUST AAI implementation and also the evolution of the EOSC-ENTRUST AAI for TREs Blueprint.

The work on this Deliverable also initiated the preparation of a separate, originally not foreseen design document on the implementation of the AAI Accounting Service [2]. This document will provide a more detailed description of the actual implementation of the Accounting service (the new, third “A”) to serve as an implementation blueprint for eventually adding Accounting for Auditing to any relevant AAI system.

7. Impact

At this moment, the training materials are of limited scope and purpose in order to support the implementation and execution of demonstrators and prototypes within the EOSC-ENTRUST project. The deliverable serves as a concise summary of the specific TRE-related background for the deployment and use of ENTRUST AAI, and to some extent, the deliverable also reflects the status of the actual implementation of the ENTRUST AAI. As such, at this stage, impact is necessarily limited, targeted primarily within the project, including both the pilots and demonstrators, and the ENTRUST AAI implementation team as a provider of feedback on the implementation itself.

8. References

- [1] **EOSC-ENTRUST D16.1 – The AAI for TREs Blueprint.** Zenodo record 15006945. <https://zenodo.org/records/15006945> Zenodo
- [2] **EADD-001: Design Document for implementing AAI Accounting Service.** Google Docs (project internal; access may require permission). <https://docs.google.com/document/d/184u-2R4nduZwEB6g7AQzjWWuSpA8ODw2/>
- [3] **TRE administrator training material** (Appendix A). Google Docs (project internal). <https://docs.google.com/document/d/104gkleJeQHvZ-CwTwqUV7uu89MDBqUk9/>

- [4] **TRE user training material** (Appendix B). Google Docs (project internal).
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1UETrrePewfMywuc0kmHkXF4LNXW7f-6N/>
- [5] **VO manager training material** (Appendix C). Google Docs (project internal).
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ClRMJcHYoIgNqK4gS7vQVHXGGk8EzcMC/>
- [6] **Life Science Login (LS AAI) – Overview page.** <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login.html>
- [7] **Documentation for connecting your service to LS AAI**
[LS Login : Service Provider Documentation | LifeScience RI](#)
- [8] **Documentation for end-users**
[LS Login : User Documentation | LifeScience RI](#)
- [9] **AARC-G069 – Guidelines for expressing group membership and role information.**
<https://zenodo.org/record/6533400/files/AARC-G069%20Guidelines%20for%20expressin%20group%20membership%20and%20role%20information.pdf>
- [10] **WISE Community – Baseline Acceptable Use Policy.**
<https://wise-community.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/WISE-SCI-Baseline-AUP-V1.pdf>
- [11] **REFEDS – Sirtfi v2 Framework for Security Incident Response.**
<https://refeds.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Sirtfi-v2.pdf>

Appendix A. TRE administrator training material

D17.1 Training material for the use of AAAI for TREs pilot implementation, Appendix A

1. Integrating TRE pilot implementation to AAAI

This appendix provides training material for **Trusted Research Environment (TRE) administrators** who are responsible for integrating their TREs with the **Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI)** developed within the EOSC ENTRUST project.

It explains the main administrative tasks and responsibilities, covering areas such as compliance with applicable policies, system integration, day-to-day operation, and available support options.

Background description (preparatory phase)

Architecture

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) aim to balance data utility for collaborative research with robust safeguards for privacy, integrity, and regulatory compliance. The integration of Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting (AAA) functions is fundamental to achieving this balance, enabling granular access control, accountability, and interoperability across services and platforms.

This section presents a generalised architecture for AAA integration in a TRE, derived from the design principles and implementation experience of the Services for Sensitive Data (TSD³), see **Figure 1**. The architecture is abstracted to guide the design of secure, scalable, and multi-tenant research infrastructures. Key architectural components, interaction patterns, and integration points are described to facilitate reproducibility and interoperability.

The following sections describe the practical steps required to connect these components within the TRE pilot.

³ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>

Figure 1: Generalised Architectural Overview of Authentication, Authorisation, and Auditing (AAA) Integration in a Trusted Research Environment (TRE)

Authentication

The authentication subsystem consists of several coordinated components. At its foundation, the central Identity and Access Management (IAM) system governs all user, project, and group identities, while also providing APIs for authentication, authorisation, and resource management. Authentication operations are facilitated by an OpenID Connect (OIDC) provider, which implements standards-based authentication flows—including Proof of Key Code Exchange (PKCE) for browser clients—and integrates with external Identity Providers to support multi-institutional access. Federated authentication enables users to log in through trusted third-party providers, simplifying account creation and management processes. The environment enforces Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA), such as Time-based One-Time Password (TOTP) or Hash-based Message Authentication Code (HMAC)-based (HOTP) One-Time Passcodes, which users can manage via a self-service portal. Token exchange mechanisms support the issuance of narrowly scoped, short-lived

API access tokens. For non-interactive or time-limited workflows, client and instance-based authentication—including “magic links”—enables automated or temporary access, with optional password protection for added security.

Authorisation

Authorisation is centrally managed by a policy enforcement engine, which serves as the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) for all API requests entering the environment through designated gateways. This engine evaluates each request against access control policies (grants) maintained within the IAM database. These policies may be static—maintained as code or configuration under version control—or dynamically managed via programmable interfaces provided by the IAM API. All access tokens and authorisation grants are strictly scoped to specific projects or tenants and to designated API gateways. Network and resource-level isolation is maintained through private VLANs and firewall policies. The authorisation workflow includes validating the token’s integrity and claims, matching access policy grants to requested API operations and contextual attributes, and enforcing any additional restrictions such as time windows or usage limits.

Auditing

Auditing is implemented across all relevant system layers to support accountability, regulatory compliance, and operational monitoring. Every API operation—spanning file, data, and resource actions—is logged in detail, with audit logs accessible for both operational staff and authorised project administrators. Changes to IAM data and resource allocations are tracked, capturing all create, update, and delete events. All storage and file access operations are monitored for data integrity and incident response purposes. Exports of data and downloads from publication interfaces are recorded to maintain a verifiable trail of data egress. Finally, system event and operations logs are aggregated and made available for ongoing monitoring, security investigations, and incident response.

Key Architectural Components and Integration Points

The environment employs multiple API gateways (external, internal, and restricted) to route all API traffic, enforce TLS, and delegate authentication and authorisation to centralised control points. A message broker enables event-driven service integrations, publishing relevant events to subscribed internal and external consumers. Microservices synchronise user, group, and project information from the IAM system to external directories as needed. Core research, compute, storage, and notification APIs all integrate directly with the central IAM for authentication and authorisation. Web-based self-service and administrative portals, as well as data collection services, interact with the AAA infrastructure for secure, auditable operations. Project-level network isolation is enforced via software-defined firewalls and VLAN segmentation, dynamically configured based on IAM and directory data.

Staff operational access is tightly regulated by IAM-based role assignment, group membership, multi-factor authentication, and the use of bastion hosts; all privileged actions are auditable.

Summary

This architecture, abstracted from the TSD model, positions a centralised IAM system at its core and integrates standards-based authentication, strict policy-driven authorisation, comprehensive audit logging, and deep project isolation. The design provides a reproducible blueprint for building secure, compliant, and multi-tenant research environments capable of handling sensitive data at scale.

Access control

To implement access control using the ENTRUST AAI, the TRE administrator should perform the following steps:

- connect the TRE services with a web interface to the AAI part that implements Identity Provider Proxy using the OpenID Connect protocol;
- connect the TRE services which are either non-web or require provisioning and deprovisioning of user accounts to the AAI part that implements Identity Management using an agreed protocol for push notifications of changes;
- deploy Attribute Based Access Control (ABAC):
 - deploy an instance of OPA (Open Policy Agent) as ABAC's PDP (Policy Decision Point);
 - connect Federation Services registries as Policy Information Points to the OPA/PDP;
 - publish access control policies as documents written in the Rego rule language processed by OPA⁴.

During the preparatory phase, the exact structure and key names for attributes must be agreed on so that the access policy Rego rules can be written to process them.

Compliance

Compliance ensures that the TRE participates in the federated AAI ecosystem responsibly and consistently with community standards.

⁴ The **Rego rule language** (<https://www.openpolicyagent.org/docs/policy-language>) is a part of the **Open Policy Agent (OPA)** framework — an open-source, CNCF-graduated project for declarative, fine-grained Authorisation across distributed systems ([Open Policy Agent - Homepage](#) | [Open Policy Agent](#)).

The TRE administrator must ensure that integration with the **Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI)** complies with the policies, security frameworks, and data protection principles adopted within the **EOSC ENTRUST** project. These obligations apply both to the technical operation of the TRE and to the organisational procedures supporting its users.

At the core of this AAI compliance framework are two key references:

- the **WISE Baseline Acceptable Use Policy (AUP)**, which defines the common rules of responsible use for all participants in federated infrastructures;
- the **Sirtfi v2 Security Incident Response Framework**, which ensures that each TRE can cooperate effectively in case of security incidents or policy breaches.

Administrators must verify that local TRE policies and user terms of use are compatible with the WISE Baseline AUP and that security contacts and procedures are registered in the appropriate federation databases as required by **Sirtfi v2**. In addition, the handling of user-related attributes and accounting records must follow the principles of data minimisation, purpose limitation, and transparency as defined by the GDPR and by the **AAAI Privacy Policy** (currently, the [Privacy Notice for LS Login](#) should be used).

The administrator is responsible for ensuring that all connected services meet these baseline requirements before they are accepted into the federated environment. This includes confirming that users authenticate via recognised Identity Providers, that appropriate assurance levels are enforced for sensitive data access, and that incident-handling and audit procedures are clearly documented and periodically tested.

Authentication

Register OIDC client

OIDC Terminology

OpenID Connect (OIDC) is a protocol specified in the [OpenID Connect Core 1.0](#) specification. It is a simple identity layer on top of the **OAuth 2.0** protocol specified in [RFC 6749](#) (“The OAuth 2.0 Authorisation Framework”), so it partly inherits its terminology and partly defines its own.

The protocols define interactions among several parties. The party that gets authorised in OAuth 2.0 is called a “**client**”; in OIDC the party that gets authorised to obtain user data is called a “**Relying Party**”, because it relies on the obtained data. An OIDC Relying Party is also an OAuth 2.0 client; thus, the term “OIDC client” is often used instead of the longer term “OIDC Relying Party”, which is more technically correct.

Similarly, the party called “**End-User**” in OIDC is called “resource owner” in OAuth 2.0, thus, these terms are also used interchangeably. A notable difference is that OIDC involves a party called “**OpenID Provider**” which simultaneously plays two roles specified in OAuth 2.0 – it is both an “**authorisation server**” and a “**resource server**”, where the only served resource is a URL providing information about users, so-called “user info endpoint”.

A service that needs to obtain information about a user is thus an “OIDC Relying Party” or “client” for short. It needs to register itself at the OpenID Provider. The registration process depends on the implementation of AAI. In the case of LifeScience login there is a dedicated web application at <https://services.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/spreg/> where the person responsible for the service needs to fill up several forms in a wizard.

Client types and grant flows

During the registration, some technical details about the client must be provided. Which details depend mainly on the **type of client** as defined in OAuth 2.0 RFC [section 2.1](#) - whether it is a client capable of maintaining the confidentiality of its credentials or not (confidential vs. public clients), and whether it is a web application, a user-agent-based application, or a mobile/native application.

Different types of clients have different security properties, thus different so-called **grant flows** are used to securely interact between the client and the authorisation server:

- a confidential client uses **Authorisation Code Grant Flow** defined in OAuth 2.0 RFC [section 4.1](#);
- a user-agent-based public client uses **Authorisation Code Grant Flow with PKCE** (Proof Key for Code Exchange, pronounced "pixy") defined in [RFC 7636](#);
- a mobile/native application uses the flow defined in [RFC 8252](#), which is an **Authorisation Code Grant Flow with PKCE** using a temporary HTTP server and an external browser;
- an application embedded in a device like in a smart TV uses **Device Authorisation Grant Flow** defined in [RFC 8628](#).

During registration of a client, the grant flow type must be selected, whether a PKCE should be used, and which hash function would be used for PKCE.

Redirect URIs

For security reasons, in the final step of a user's interaction with the OpenID Provider during authentication, the user's browser can be redirected back to the client only to a URL from a fixed set of URLs registered for the given client. These URLs must be absolute URLs without any wildcard characters. As specified in [RFC 9700 Section 2.1](#), exact string matching is

required for redirect URIs, except for the port number when using localhost. The set of URLs must be provided during client registration.

Scopes

OAuth 2.0 defines (in [section 3.3](#)) so-called **scopes** as a list of space-delimited strings that limit usage of an access token. OIDC defines (in [section 5.4](#)) specific scopes for obtaining user **claims**, like email, name, address and so on. Additionally, the AARC (Authentication and authorisation for Research and Collaboration) guidelines specify some other scopes and claims useful in federated research environments.

A client should at least request the “**openid**” scope which asks for releasing the “**sub**” (subject) claim containing the user identifier. The “**profile**” scope asks for releasing multiple claims including name, time zone and locale (preferred language). The “**email**” scope asks for releasing the “**email**” claim containing the email address. The special “**offline_access**” scope enables obtaining refresh tokens that can be used for retrieving access tokens without user intervention, which may be beneficial e.g. in long-running computations, but the OIDC specification requires that a consent page is always displayed for such grants.

The AARC’s special scope “**entitlements**” (defined in [AARC-G069](#) as a replacement for the older “**eduperson_entitlement**” defined in [AARC-G002](#)) asks for the release of an identically named claim that is the OIDC version of the [eduPersonEntitlement](#) SAML attribute. It contains a list of URNs that correspond to a set of rights to resources. It is the recommended way to express information intended for authorisation, like group membership, in OIDC.

OIDC Client Configuration

After successful client registration, the following values need to be configured in the OIDC client:

- a URL of **OpenID Provider metadata** (as defined in [OpenID Connect Discovery 1.0](#) specification);
- a client identifier known as a **client_id** (as defined in OAuth 2.0 RFC [section 2.3.1](#));
- a client password known as a **client_secret** is provided for confidential clients; it is not provided for public clients because public clients cannot keep secrets;
- list of **scopes** to request.

The OpenID Provider metadata is a JSON-formatted document containing the URLs of various protocol endpoints, supported ciphers, supported scopes, and other useful metadata describing the capabilities of that particular OpenID Provider. The metadata URL is provided in the AAI documentation; currently, we use the LifeScience AAI documentation <https://login.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/oidc/well-known/openid-configuration>

The **client_id** and **client_secret** are credentials needed by the client to exchange an authorisation code for an access token in some grant flows. In other flows, just **client_id** with some additional security measures is needed. The values are provided after the client registration.

Authorisation

The authorisation model used in the [AAAI for TREs Blueprint](#) is the **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)** framework implemented using **Open Policy Agent (OPA)** as its **Policy Decision Point (PDP)**. The access decisions made by PDP should be enforced at **Policy Enforcement Points (PEP)**, which are application-specific, e.g., when controlling access to a file at a file server, the PEP would be a part of the file server.

ABAC makes access decisions by evaluating rules contained in an **access policy** against the attributes of **subject** (the entity attempting to access a resource), **object** (the resource being accessed), **operation** (the action being attempted), and **environment** (the context of the access, like time, location, or other aspects).

The OIDC **entitlement claims** described in the previous section can be used as one of the sources of user attributes for authorisation decisions. It contains URNs (Universal Resource Names) that correspond to rights to resources. The AARC documents [AARC-G069 Guidelines for expressing group membership and role information](#) and [AARC-G027 Guidelines for expressing resource capabilities](#) describe how to encode group memberships, roles, and permitted actions on resources as URNs.

These entitlements should be viewed as user attributes in ABAC. Other sources of attributes for **user**, **object**, **operation**, and **environment** would be the various registries defined in the [EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Blueprint](#) section 6.2.1 Federation Services, which lists:

- users registry
- projects registry
- datasets registry
- federation participants registry

It also mentions training and certification of users, but leaves it for the AAAI instead of a separate registry; thus, training and certification records are likely to be provided as URNs in the `eduperson_entitlement` claim, being modeled as group memberships in AAAI.

All the attributes would be fed into an access control policy in OPA. An access policy in OPA is a text file containing a set of rules in the special [Rego](#) language.

When an access policy is invoked, its rules are evaluated on the given input, which is a JSON-formatted document, and produce a JSON-formatted output, which should contain the key “**allow**” with the boolean value **true** or **false** for permitting or denying access respectively.

Implement access control policies

Access control policies in OPA are written in the Rego language. Its extensive documentation is available at [OPA Policy Language](#). A policy can be a single file, or it can be modularised by invoking other policy files registered in the same instance of OPA. Policy files are identified by package names in OPA, like in the Python programming language, thus forming a tree. This would allow generalisation of common parts of a policy, and implementation of specialised parts of the policy in deployment-specific variants.

All the information that should be taken into account by a policy needs to be encoded as JSON. A lot of information is already in JSON, namely the user claims obtained from OIDC user info endpoint, or the content of OIDC id token that contains information about the current authentication session (like whether multi-factor authentication was performed).

Other attributes coming from the Federation Services registries should be converted into JSON in the expected structure. A possible problem may be that the APIs for the Federation Services are not specified yet, so there are no standards on how the attributes coming from them would be named or structured yet.

Connect policy information points

The section [External Data](#) in Open Policy Agent documentations discusses the options for how to provide data for a policy. Depending on the amount of data, the requirements for data freshness, and the requirements for response times, the recommended options are [Option 4: Push Data](#) and [Option 5: Pull Data during Evaluation](#). The push data option minimises the time needed for evaluating a policy while keeping reasonable freshness of data. The pull data during evaluation option ensures the freshest data by pulling them in at the moment they are needed, at the expense of making policy evaluation take longer by waiting for the fresh data to be downloaded every time.

Set up access deprovisioning

If access deprovisioning is required, the OpenID Connect protocol is not enough, because it provides info about a user at the moment of authentication, or when the user info endpoint is called later. It does not provide a mechanism for notifying the Relying Party that the user account should be deleted or disabled.

For this, a **push-strategy Identity Management** is needed. An **Identity Management** part of the AAAI can push events to registered services, like when a new user becomes a member of a group, or when a user ceases to be a member of a group, or a user ceases to be a user in AAAI at all.

This push mechanism is AAAI-implementation dependent. In LS AAI, it is based on connections using the SSH (Secure Shell) protocol, pushing JSON-formatted files containing information about users and groups. The service has to accept LS AAI's ssh key for enabling the ssh connections, install a DEB or RPM package with software receiving the files, and optionally write its own code that gets invoked after each push event to process the newly arrived data.

Group-based access control

If full ABAC would be an overkill, a simpler approach might be to do authorisation using group memberships. This would actually be an instance of the Role Based Access Control model in which groups emulate roles. In LS AAI, a Virtual Organization can have any number of groups, where groups form [rooted trees](#) with ancestor groups containing all members of descendant groups. Where a more general graph than a tree may be needed, a special link between two groups can be made by including all members of one group in another group.

The group membership information can be provided either through the entitlements claim in OIDC protocol, or in JSON-formatted files using the push provisioning mechanism described in the previous section.

Accounting for Auditing

The AAAI will provide an integrated Accounting Service to support auditing and accountability requirements in Trusted Research Environments (TREs). This is essential for enabling traceability of user actions and access to sensitive data.

Note: The design of the EOSC ENTRUST Accounting for Auditing system is currently in draft form and is being piloted. The initial implementation leverages the ELK stack (Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana) to collect, index, and visualise audit events.

Audit Event Model

A shared Audit Event Model is proposed to structure the data collected across AAAI components and connected TRE services. This model ensures consistency, enabling event correlation and compliance reporting.

Each audit event should include the following fields:

- **timestamp**: When the event occurred, including timezone
- **source**: The system, component, or service that generated the event
- **subject**: The authenticated user who triggered the action
- **object**: The resource being accessed (e.g., file, dataset, service)
- **operation**: The type of action attempted (e.g., read, delete, view)
- **outcome**: Whether the action was successful, failed, or unknown
- **reason** (*optional*): Reference to a policy or rule influencing the outcome
- **origin system**: Where the event originated (e.g., home Identity Provider)
- **destination system**: The target service accessed
- **protocol**: The protocol used (e.g., OIDC, SAML, SSH)
- **ip address**: Source IP address of the user's device
- **correlation ID** (*optional*): A unique identifier to link related events across systems

The **correlation ID**, while not mandatory in all cases, may be used internally to group events that originate from a single user session for interaction across multiple services. It is generated by the AAAI that handles a user request and may be propagated through the AAAI to the TRE services.

Implementation Notes

In the pilot deployment:

- Logs are shipped to a central ELK stack for aggregation, indexing, and auditing.
- Logstash pipelines normalise the event fields according to the Audit Event Model.
- Kibana dashboards support manual inspection and visualization of access patterns.
- Access to audit data is controlled and governed by appropriate access policies.

Deploy the accounting connector

To enable accounting:

- Deploy and configure the Accounting Connector in each TRE service.
- Ensure correlation ID propagation from the AAAI components to TRE services.
- Log user actions with required metadata in a structured format.
- Provide rules to translate the individual structured format to the Audit Event Model format.

Note: This section will be updated as the ENTRUST Accounting for Auditing pilot progresses to include more concrete guidelines, such as refined versions of the audit event model, configuration templates for integrating TRE services with the central logging infrastructure, and example Kibana dashboards for common auditing and compliance scenarios. Future

versions will also incorporate best practices for log retention, access control, and anomaly detection, based on experience from pilot deployments and feedback.

Appendix B. TRE user training material

D17.1 Training material for the use of AAAI for TREs pilot implementation, Appendix B

1. Introduction

This appendix provides guidance for end-users of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) connected to the ENTRUST Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI). It describes the typical user lifecycle, from registration to account closure, and explains basic security responsibilities.

It complements the overview presented in the main D17.1 document.

2. Account management

Registration process

The first step every TRE user must do when using TRE AAAI for access is to register in the TRE AAAI. Registration is a mechanism for AAAI account creation and obtaining membership in Virtual Organisations and groups. It is also the step where the user is informed about their rights and responsibilities, and where they give necessary consents.

From the user's perspective, they start by using the provided link, continue by logging in using their academic Identity Provider (or social Identity Provider if they don't have one), and finish by filling in and submitting an application form. The user may be asked to verify their email address.

Linking digital identities

A TRE user has an option to link additional digital identities to their AAAI account. The main benefit is that they do not lose access to their AAAI account if they lose access to one of their identities (e.g., losing a university account after their contract ends). The downside is that some digital identities (esp. social identities) are not considered trustworthy enough for TRE use.

From the user's perspective, they start by logging in using an existing digital identity, then follow the AAAI process for identity linking, which in the end requires them to log in with the digital identity they wish to link.

Identity proofing

A basic requirement of TREs is that they know users' legal identities for accounting and auditing purposes. Thus, as a prerequisite for TRE use, a TRE user must undergo the AAAI identity proofing process so that their legal identity can be established and recorded.

From the user's perspective, they start by logging in using an existing digital identity, then follow the AAAI process for identity proofing, which in the end requires them to use some external tool (eID portal, ID card scanner, present EUDI wallet, academic IdP with adequate identity assurance, etc.)

MFA setup

Another basic requirement of TREs is that users log in using secure methods. Currently, MFA is the best approach, balancing security and usability. However, it does require initial setup.

In the best-case scenario, MFA is supported by their primary academic Identity Provider, and the user is already used to using it there. As a backup option, AAAI can provide MFA on its own if none of the linked Identity Providers support it.

If the user must use, or chooses to use, MFA provided by AAAI, they must set it up. From their perspective, they start by logging in using an existing digital identity, then follow the AAAI process for MFA setup, and finish by saving the backup codes!

Account lifecycle

Account closing

A TRE user's AAAI account will eventually be closed if not used, so that their personal data is not stored indefinitely.

Account extension

A TRE user is notified before their AAAI account expires, giving them a chance to extend its use. The user must apply for an extension, which may be subject to approval in some cases.

From the user's perspective, they start by using the provided link, continue by logging in using an existing digital identity, and finish by submitting an extension request. The user may be asked to provide additional information (e.g., a justification).

Account renewal

Generally, it shouldn't be possible for a TRE user to renew a closed AAAI account. They must register a new AAAI account instead.

This is because AAAI must delete (or anonymise) user accounts on closing and must forbid reuse of user identifiers, making it impossible to associate any user with those identifiers (and transitively, permissions) ever again.

3. Logging into TREs

Login process

A TRE user must be logged into a TRE (i.e. authenticated) to use it. Additionally, the user must be logged into AAAI to use TRE federation services or execute cross-TRE workflows.

From the user's perspective, the login process typically begins when they access a TRE or a service, continues with the selection of an Identity Provider, the presentation of credentials for authentication and additional factors for MFA, and ends by redirecting the user back to the TRE or service.

User session

AAAI provides a single sign-on (SSO) mechanism, meaning a TRE user need not log in again for the duration of their session, i.e., until they log out or until the session expires. AAAI session length must balance usability (not too short) and security (not too long).

Logout process

A TRE user can and should log out from a TRE when they no longer plan to use it. This action may trigger a single log-out (SLO).

4. Permissions

Gaining access

Requesting access

A TRE user uses AAAI to request access to individual TREs and to TRE federation services.

From the user's perspective, they start by using the provided link, continue by logging in using an existing digital identity, and finish by submitting an application form. Following application approval, the user becomes a member of a Virtual Organisation and one or more groups that entitle them to a TRE or service access.

Justifying the request

TRE operator or VO manager may optionally require a written justification from the TRE user to approve their request. From the user's perspective, they just have to fill in an extra field in the application form before submitting it.⁵

Losing access

Expired access

A TRE user's access (represented by VO and group membership) will eventually expire to prevent indefinite access to TREs or services. The period is set by the VO manager.

Revoked access

A TRE user may also have their access revoked by TRE operator or VO manager, e.g. if the user breaks the rules or it is suspected that their account has been compromised.

5. Audit

What auditing means for you as a TRE user

Auditing refers to the ability of the system to **record, trace, and review actions** taken by users within the AAI and TRE environments. These actions may include logging in, accessing services or datasets, and requesting or losing access. The goal is to ensure **accountability**, support **security investigations**, and comply with legal and ethical frameworks. Auditing helps maintain trust in the TRE ecosystem and ensures that research data is used responsibly.

As a TRE user, this means:

- Your actions in the TRE and related services are logged securely.
- The logs may be used to verify that access was legitimate.
- Only authorised personnel (e.g., security teams, auditors) can access audit information.
- No personal data is shared beyond what is necessary for security and compliance
- You can request a review of your own activity if needed (see below).

⁵ Virtual Organisation (VO) refers to individuals responsible for managing group or project memberships, access policies, and enrollment workflows within the virtual organisations integrated with the ENTRUST AAI (e.g. those established for specific Trusted Research Environments or scientific collaborations).

Self-review

A TRE user may use their AAAI user profile to check the date and time of their last login, per digital identity. This section will be expanded once the ENTRUST AAAI service offers a user-accessible auditing interface with extended functionality.

6. Using TREs pilot implementation with AAAI

Responsibilities

A TRE user has some responsibilities when using AAAI:

- All users act under the Acceptable Use Policy and Privacy Notice (currently using the LS Login one, i.e., [LS Login AUP](#) and [LS Login Privacy Notice](#))
- Secure their user account against misuse, loss, or theft
- Cooperate with the AAAI operator on request
- Keep all their information up to date
- Not to misuse system errors to gain higher privileges, but report these to the AAAI operator instead
- Report the loss or misuse of their access data to the appropriate CSIRT
 - <https://csirt.muni.cz/en> for LS AAI

Support options

A TRE user has two support options at their disposal:

- AAAI end-user documentation
 - <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login.html> for LS AAI
- AAAI user support staff
 - support@aai.lifescience-ri.eu for LS AAI

Users are encouraged to contact support proactively in case of access issues or suspected security incidents.

Appendix C. VO manager training material

D17.1 Training material for the use of AAI for TREs pilot implementation, Appendix C

This appendix provides practical guidance for **Virtual Organisation (VO)**⁶ managers operating within the ENTRUST **Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI)**. It explains the VO lifecycle, membership management, attribute collection, and audit practices used to keep access aligned with project needs and policy obligations. It complements the overview in the main D17.1 and should be read together with the relevant LS Login documentation.

1. VO management

A Virtual Organisation (VO) is a structure created within the AAAI that allows the aggregation and management of users, services, and resources for a specific purpose. The VO facilitates easy coordination of resources, management of user accounts, and setting access permissions, supporting effective collaboration on research initiatives.

A TRE will be represented by a VO in the AAAI system with the TRE administrator acting as VO admin. This allows TRE admins to define groups and group memberships for access control to the TRE (see [Access control](#) for more information). Data holders will be considered “Secure Data Zone only TREs” (SDZ-only TRE) and represented by a VO in the AAAI system.

However, it is important to note that VO managers manage **membership and group structure** in the AAAI; **TRE administrators** configure and enforce authorisation in the TRE based on those memberships.

A research community (e.g., research institution or group) may be represented by a VO in the AAAI system with community leaders acting as VO managers. Community structure can be represented by group memberships under the VO as needed.

⁶ Virtual Organisation (VO) refers to individuals responsible for managing group or project memberships, access policies, and enrollment workflows within the virtual organisations integrated with the ENTRUST AAAI (e.g. those established for specific Trusted Research Environments or scientific collaborations).

VO lifecycle

A VO is created by the AAAI Operations Team upon request from the applicant. The VO will have a lifetime based on the need for the VO as expressed in the request. The lifetime can be reviewed and extended as needed.

User registration process

User registration happens through a membership application form managed by the VO Manager. Usually, two versions of the form are created: one for the initial application for joining a VO and one for extending membership in a VO after membership expiration.

The AAAI system collects and releases a standard set of attributes for each user. The initial VO membership application form should collect any attributes needed by the VO that will be used for AAAI purposes in addition to this standard set of attributes. However, the AAAI system only collects attributes needed for policy decisions (data minimisation) and, where required, ensures appropriate assurance (identity proofing/MFA) is in place for access to sensitive attributes.

User application approval can be either manual or automatic, as chosen by the VO Manager. Usually, manual approval is used for the initial membership, and automatic approval is used for extending the membership after expiration.

User attribute collection

The standard identity attributes (name, email, identifier, affiliation) collected and released by the AAAI system are received from the user's home organisation when the user logs in. Any attributes required in addition to these standard attributes are collected via the VO membership application. Membership information required for access control is expressed via group registration and membership (see [Access control](#) section for more information).

User expiration process

The VO Manager can set membership expiration rules for the VO or manually for individual users. Membership in a VO expires after one year (12 months) by default.

Membership expiration rules are based on time, either on a static date or a dynamic time period. Expiration based on a static date will expire all memberships in a VO once a year on the given date. Expiration based on a dynamic time period will expire memberships once the given period of time has passed from the membership application approval for each individual user.

Access control

Access control is based on group memberships controlled by individual TREs. VO Manager can create groups as needed and assign Group Manager duties to manage group memberships for individual groups. The recommended structure is to have one group for general access to the TRE with subgroups representing individual projects for project-specific access. More levels of subgroups can be created representing objects of interest within projects, like zones, groups, datasets, etc. Membership in the “TRE Users” group is derived from membership in a project-specific group, automatically making group management easier. In case of federated projects that span multiple TREs, the preferred approach is to have an a priori agreement on a shared VO (the federated VO), group, and subgroup (particular project) that is accepted by all TREs in the federation that are expected to run the federated workflow. If this is not possible, users must ensure, before the actual federated workflow run, that they are registered in VOs, groups, or subgroups of each individual per TRE VO.

To ensure portability across services, group/role information should follow community guidance for expressing entitlements over OIDC (see [AARC-G069](#)).

2. Audit

Regular audits help ensure that access to Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and their resources is granted appropriately, remains aligned with users’ roles, and is revoked when no longer justified. VO Managers are responsible for monitoring access for users from the time they join the VO until their membership expires or is revoked.

Review access request

VO Managers should review access request records. These include:

- User identity information (e.g., name, affiliation, persistent identifier),
- Timestamp of the access request,
- Attributes or statements provided during registration (e.g., purpose of access, project name),
- Requested access levels or group memberships,
- Level of Assurance (LoA) associated with the user’s identity.

This review process supports transparency and accountability by verifying that applications include all required information and are aligned with the VO's access policies.

Review access grant

To ensure that access to the TRE and its resources has been granted appropriately, VO Managers should regularly review group memberships and membership status within the

VO. Access control is primarily based on group membership, which reflects the user's approved purpose of access.

During the review, VO Managers should check whether users remain eligible based on the purpose of their membership and whether their group memberships are consistent with the VO's access control policies. This includes verifying that any additional conditions for access, such as a required Level of Assurance (LoA), are still being met.

Such reviews help ensure that access remains aligned with project needs and user roles as defined by the VO's structure. They should be carried out on a regular basis, and also in response to any reported security incidents, changes in policy, or concerns about inappropriate access.

Due diligence

Maintaining appropriate access involves regular due diligence, including:

- Ensuring memberships are renewed only if users still meet eligibility criteria,
- Verifying that attributes used for access control (e.g., affiliation, assurance level, group membership) remain current,
- Revoking access when users are no longer involved in a project or affiliated with a trusted organisation.

Automated processes for expiration and renewal should be complemented by periodic manual review.

Looking for irregularities

Audit activities should include checks for potential irregularities such as:

- Users with unexpected combinations of groups/roles or access levels,
- Users accessing sensitive resources with an insufficient level of assurance,
- Users appearing multiple times under different identities – potentially due to using different trusted identity providers without linking their profiles – which may lead to confusion or policy inconsistencies,
- Accounts for users who have left the organisation but were not deprovisioned.

Irregularities may indicate misconfiguration or abuse and should be investigated further.

Looking for bottlenecks

VO Managers should also monitor the efficiency of access workflows to identify and resolve operational bottlenecks. Examples include:

- Excessive delays in reviewing or approving access requests,
- Unresponsive group or role managers,
- Redundant manual steps that could be automated,

- Lack of standardised criteria for approving or rejecting access requests.

Monitoring approval timelines and request completion rates helps maintain a responsive and user-friendly access process.

Looking for overprovisioning

Users and services may accumulate excessive permissions over time. Signs to watch for include:

- Users with access to more systems or roles than needed for their current responsibilities,
- Service accounts with broader access than justified by their purpose,
- Permissions granted "just in case" or for temporary use, but never revoked,
- Lack of adherence to the principle of least privilege.